

Improving ED Throughput: Initiation of a New Standard Protocol

Katrina Thoa Trinh Wallace, DNP, RN ❖ Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP-BC ❖ Cinthya Sotelo, DNP, FNP-C

Background

- *Overcrowding* occurs when the number of patients exceeds the capability of the ED to safely & efficiently provide quality care
- Causes long wait times and higher morbidity and mortality rates
- Standardized protocol (SP) can help mitigate factors that contributes to this

Purpose

- Implementation of a new SP to alleviate ED overcrowding, improve throughput and ED metrics
- Developed an Electronic Self-Learning Module (ELM) to train triage RN on the new SP to improve triage process

Standard Protocol

- Evidence-based set of medical orders used as guideline for chief complaints
- Initiate diagnostic testing and therapeutic management in triage, prior to assessments
- Diagnostic test results completed → expediting ED physician decision making → Improves ED throughput

Methods

- Determined need for credible triage training for new SP to improve triage
- Literature review for appropriate pedagogy in several areas
- Research conducted for more effective teaching: Use of Pre-Posttests, Quizzes, Course Objectives and Evaluations
- Develop/design ELM to train triage RNs
- ELM evaluated by 2 Certified Nursing Professional Development Educator
- ELM revision based on recommendations

Theoretical Framework

4. ACT: What changes will you make based on your findings?

- Adopt/modify → repeat cycle
- Abandon project/change approach → repeat cycle
- Adopt

3. STUDY: What are the results?

- Analyze data
- Evaluate the process
- Summarize what was learned

1. PLAN: What are you going to do?

- Project's goals
- Measurable outcomes
- Stakeholders
- Plan to Implement

2. DO: Where and how do you do it?

- Implementation
- Data collection
- Document observation

PDSA Model courtesy of The W. Edwards Deming Institute

ED Standardized Procedure: Diagnostic Protocol for Triage

Electronic Learning Module

Purpose	Examples of Chief Complaints	Key Contents
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Educate triage nurse on the clinical approach to identify potential diagnoses of chief complaints ▪ Triage nurses will understand and independently initiate appropriate ED order-sets and follow treatment guidelines for triaged patients ▪ To have patients complete diagnostic tests and initiate treatment before evaluation from ED MD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Anaphylaxis with Hypotension/ ▪ Unstable Airway ▪ Chest pain ▪ Seizures ▪ Head injury (trauma) ▪ Respiratory distress ▪ Discusses patient physical exam and importance of patient interview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EBP order-set guidelines for patients with common chief complaints and s/s presenting to ED ▪ Module contains course purpose, learning objectives, new ED SP guidelines; Provides chief complaint, definition, symptoms, pathophysiology, physical findings, diagnostic studies, treatments and possible diagnosis ▪ Includes Pre-Posttests, Course objectives, evaluation, and quizzes

Implementation & Evaluation Plan

- Pilot ELM with 5 triage nurses
- Initiate pre-intervention survey
- Initiate ELM training to all ED triage RNs (including pre-post-test)
- Commence hands-on-training in triage
- Gather retrospective de-identified data
- Data collection-6 months implementation
- Statistical analysis of all data
- Compare ED metrics pre and post-intervention: Door-to-decision, Door-to-discharge, Door-to-admit, and Left Without Being Seen rates
- Interpretation of data outcome. Did it make a difference? Did it improve ED throughput? Impact of outcome?

Implications for Nursing Practice

- Triage is an advanced nursing skill using critical thinking and clinical judgment
- With SP, triage nurse can function independently initiating appropriate ED order-sets and following simple treatment guidelines
- If RN performs effective triaging, patient care is better

Conclusion

- An EBP SP in triage can expedite the patient care process and improve ED metrics and ED throughput
- ELM provides the triage nurse with the critical information needed to address patient symptoms and chief complaints in a systematic approach